

A Review of the Inaugural Edition of the African Journal of Paediatric Neurology and Developmental Medicine

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This inaugural edition of the African Journal of Paediatric Neurology and Developmental Medicine (AJPNDM), contains commentaries on the practice of paediatric neurology in general, and articles on some specific childhood neurological disorders namely: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), epilepsy, and sleep disorders.

Research into paediatric neurological disorders provide insights into dynamics of these disorders, inform the basis for therapeutic interventions and preventive strategies against these disorders. The AJPNDM provides a platform to present these research and related findings, exchange information and ideas as well as strengthen the practice of paediatric neurology in the African region and globally. These expectations and more are captured by Prof Gabriel E. Ofovwwe, a distinguished Nigerian paediatric neurologist and pioneer president of the Child Neurology Society of Nigeria (CNSN), in his perspectives on the role of this journal in developing paediatric neurology practice in Africa. He opines that the journal support this development by disseminating and promoting ethical, current, and standard research findings while catalyzing international collaboration.

The practice of paediatric neurology in the African region is evolving and fraught with challenges.¹ The progress and challenges are typified in the narrative by Prof Hamidu Ahmed, another distinguished Nigerian paediatric neurologist and member of CNSN Board of Trustees, in his chronicles on the child neurology practice in Nigeria. He highlights the role of individuals and institutions in the journey of advancing child neurology practice in Nigeria. He advocates strengthening preventive measures against preventable causes of childhood neurological disorders; increasing access to diagnostic facilities, treatment and rehabilitation services; and focused training of neuro paediatricians.

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder of increasing public health concern affecting about 1 in 100 children.² Identification and management of ASD in Africa is quite challenging.^{2,3} Early identification and increasing access to care facilities have been associated with better health outcomes in children with ASD.² In their study on predictors of age at ASD diagnosis in Port Harcourt, Southern Nigeria, Gabriel-Job and Woko identified presence of a comorbidity among other factors. Also, the study reports a mean period of 36 months between the observation of symptoms and diagnosis of ASD. The study underscores the need for development of capacity in the early identification, diagnosis, and institution of care for children with ASD.

Attaining the serum therapeutic levels of Anti-Epileptic Drugs (AEDs) is crucial to achieving seizure control in children with epilepsy and optimising health outcomes. Therapeutic Drug Monitoring (TDM) can be carried out using blood, urine, or saliva.⁴ The resources for assessing the serum therapeutic levels of the AEDs is often scarce in developing countries. Assessment of the concentration of these drugs in saliva provides a veritable, non-invasive, and low cost option for monitoring the serum levels of these drugs.⁴ The study of Yusuf et al from Sokoto in North Western Nigeria show a strong correlation between serum and saliva levels of AEDs in children with epilepsy. Their study highlights the potential role of saliva in the TDM of AEDs especially in resource scarce settings.

Sleep disorders can affect the quality of life of children and adolescents.^{5,6,7} Also, they could underline the presence of disorders such as adenotonsillar hypertrophy, craniofacial anomalies, and neurological disorders.^{5,8} Showunmi et al in their study, examined the sleep pattern of children and adolescents in Ilorin, North Central Nigeria. Irregularities with sleep and wake time as well as excessive day time sleepiness were the commonest findings in their study. Their findings, and as recommended in their study, underscore the need to screen for sleep disorders in routine paediatric practice.

Caregiver burden can adversely affect health outcomes in childhood epilepsy.⁹ Psychopathologies have been identified as predictors of burden among caregivers of children with epilepsy.^{9,10} Akpan et al examined the prevalence and severity of depression among a

cohort of caregivers of children with epilepsy in Southern Nigeria. The study reports a high prevalence of depressive symptoms among the caregivers. The study underscores the need to constantly evaluate and address psychopathologies among caregivers of children with epilepsy to improve their health and social outcomes.

Hammond et al highlight some of the pertinent issues associated with the use of the electroencephalogram (EEG) in the management of childhood epilepsy in Ghana. The availability, accessibility, and affordability of neurodiagnostic tests such as the EEG have been described as essential in bridging the 'diagnostic gaps' in epilepsy. The study by Hammond et al throws up some of the challenges and steps to overcoming them.

Public health interventions are critical to addressing the burden of infectious diseases and theoretical frameworks are the bedrock of such interventions. A One Health Model (OHM), is proposed by Prof Eseigbe to address central nervous system infections, in his letter to the editor.

This inaugural edition of the AJPNDM has contained in it a variety of commentaries and studies on the practice of paediatric neurology and neurodevelopmental paediatrics in the African region. Information gathered could facilitate the development of care capacity, strengthen provision of health services, and inform future research in these fields of paediatric neurology and developmental medicine especially in the African region. The AJPNDM welcomes similar scholarly contributions from the African region and globally.

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